

FROM COUCH TO CLASSROOM: HOW PARENTING, EMOTIONS, AND HABITS INTERTWINE IN ADOLESCENT ACADEMICS

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16260632>

Received	Revised	Accepted	Published
18 April, 2025	29 May, 2025	29 June, 2025	21 July, 2025

ABSTRACT

The current study aimed to explore the relationship between perceived parental styles, sedentary behavior, emotional intelligence, and academic problems in adolescents. A Correlational research design was used to conduct the study. The data was collected from the Private and government schools and colleges of Lahore. A purposive sampling technique was used to gather data from 300 participants including 154 boys and 146 girls. Perceived Parental Styles Scale (PPSS), Sedentary Behavior Scale (SBS), Wong and Law Emotional Intelligence Scale (WLEIS), and School Children Problem Scale (SCPS-PA) were used to collect information from the participants. The results revealed that warmth parenting has a significant negative correlation with academic problems ($r = -0.11, p < 0.05$). Moreover, warmth parenting had a positive and significant relationship with emotional intelligence ($r = 0.25, p < 0.001$) while it has a significant negative relationship with academic problems ($r = 0.11, p < 0.05$). The sedentary behavior scale had a significant positive relationship with academic problems ($r = 0.25, p < 0.001$). However, screen usage also had a significant positive relationship with academic problems ($r = 0.25, p < 0.001$). Lack of physical activity had a significant negative correlation with emotional intelligence ($r = -0.12, p < 0.01$) and a significant positive correlation with academic problems ($r = 0.15, p < 0.001$). Furthermore, emotional intelligence and academic problems are significantly negatively correlated with each other ($r = 0.23, p < 0.001$). This study reveals that parenting styles are significantly correlated with academic problems and sedentary behaviors are negatively correlated with emotional intelligence while emotional intelligence is also negatively correlated with academic problems. This study will provide vital information on the effect of parenting on academic problems.

Keywords: Parenting styles, Warmth parenting, Control parenting, Sedentary behaviors, Emotional intelligence, Academic problems.

INTRODUCTION

Adolescence is one of the most crucial transitions in life, marked by significant changes. These changes are not limited to physical growth but also encompass psychological, emotional, and social development. This phase is also characterized by personal and professional growth, as individuals focus on their careers,

build intimate and mature relationships, and strive to become responsible citizens. However, pubertal changes are among the most challenging aspects of this stage, occurring differently in each gender. However, most individuals are only aware of the physical changes they experience, which can create disturbances in their lives due to a lack

of knowledge on how to manage these challenges. For instance, females begin experiencing menstruation, and males start having ejaculations, which may cause confusion or distress if they are not adequately informed (Campisi et al., 2020). Parenting plays a crucial role in this stage, as parents help their children develop a better understanding of pubertal changes. Their guidance and support can ease the transition, ensuring that adolescents navigate these changes with confidence and awareness (Hellström & Beckman, 2021).

Perceived parenting styles are the perceptions of children about their parents and their involvement in their lives and activities. Parenting styles are a broad category that includes attitudes, behaviors, values, beliefs, and actions that parents exhibit while interacting with their children. Whereas how children interpret and respond to them is termed as perceived parenting. Parenting is often measured in two domains including warmth and control. Warmth is the degree of love, affection, and emotional responsibility that parents show towards their children while control involves the strictness, discipline, boundaries, and restrictions imposed by parents for their children (Ang et al., 2018). However, warmth is often termed as a positive side of parenting while control is considered a negative side of parenting. However, according to Baumrind's model, both of these two domains are necessary for healthy parenting which Baumrind termed as authoritative parenting. This parenting has a balanced amount of warmth and control. Since parenting involves active participation in a child's life, it also plays a crucial role in shaping the child's activity levels and sedentary behaviors. Parents who encourage physical activity, set limits on screen time, and engage in active play with their children promote healthier lifestyles. Conversely, a lack of parental involvement or overly permissive parenting may lead to increased sedentary behaviors, such as excessive screen time and reduced physical activity, which can impact a child's overall well-being (Marcone et al., 2017).

Sedentary behaviors are the types of behaviors that require low amounts of physical activity and low energy expenditure. The minimal amount of energy is being used by individuals during sedentary behaviors. It includes those activities

that require sitting and lying behaviors such as watching TV, reading, using mobile phones, prolonged sitting for school or office work, playing video games, and much more. It is also defined as more than 6 hours of sitting and lying behaviors and activities consuming 1.5 metabolic equivalents. Sedentary behavior is often seen under the category of screen time (Mitchell & Byun, 2023). Screen time refers to the excessive usage of electronic devices including mobile phones, laptops, and video games. Because in today's world, people are mostly involved in sedentary behaviors while using electronic devices and it is considered one of the most important reasons for increasing sedentary behaviors, especially in adolescence. Research has shown that individuals with excessive screen time have high levels of frustration, irritability, and anger issues. Thus, sedentary behaviors also affect the emotional intelligence of individuals (Park et al., 2020).

Emotional intelligence refers to the ability to identify, comprehend, control, and regulate one's own emotions. It also includes an individual's perception and ability to understand other's emotions. In this way, it helps individuals in building healthy interpersonal relationships, and social interactions (Luna et al., 2021). Furthermore, emotional intelligence also helps in communication which helps individuals in personal and professional growth. According to Goleman's Emotional Intelligence Model (1995), this variable is defined by five key domains including self-awareness, self-regulation, motivation, empathy, and social skills. This highlights the significance of emotional intelligence in both personal and interpersonal aspects of life. However, an important aspect of life in adolescent life is academic achievement which is also influenced by emotional intelligence as it also affects the cognitive functioning of individuals. Disturbances in regulating emotions effectively can cause academic problems and difficulties.

Academic problems are the difficulties and hindrances that students face during their educational journey. It affects the student's achievement, performance, and success in their academic period. It is often assessed in relation to the individual's age group to determine whether they are achieving milestones comparable to their

peers. In addition to grades and educational success, academic problems also extend to co-curricular activities. Nowadays achieving high grades is not only important in assessing one's progress but social and educational activities are equally important in assessing one's progress (Luna et al., 2021). So, it is a multidimensional aspect that measures the cognitive as well as social abilities of individuals.

In Pakistani culture, understanding perceived parenting styles is essential, as parenting in a collectivistic society differs significantly from that in an individualistic culture. Adolescents' experiences of pubertal changes are influenced by their perception of parenting styles, shaping their emotional and psychological development. According to Erikson, adolescence is the stage of identity vs. role confusion, where identity formation is deeply impacted by how individuals navigate pubertal changes. This process further influences their emotional, psychological, and social well-being, affecting their long-term goals and career choices (Mahmood et al., 2019). Therefore, developing self-awareness and social skills at this stage is crucial for ensuring a stable and successful future.

Objectives

- To explore the relationship between perceived parental styles, sedentary behavior, emotional intelligence, and academic problems in adolescents.

Hypothesis

- It is hypothesized that there will be a significant relationship between perceived parental styles, sedentary behavior, emotional intelligence, and academic problems.
- It is hypothesized that warmth parenting will have a significant negative correlation with academic problems.
- It is hypothesized that control parenting, sedentary behavior and academic problems will have a positive relationship.

Methodology

Research Design

A correlational research design was used to determine the relationship between study variables.

Sampling Strategy

Data was collected from adolescent students using purposive sampling. This strategy was chosen to ensure the selection of participants who met the specific inclusion and exclusion criteria of the study.

Sample

The sample consisted of individuals aged 14 to 18 years. The study included 300 participants, with an almost equal distribution of genders, including 146 girls and 154 boys.

Setting

For this study, data were collected from school and college students in Lahore. Participants were selected from the 9th, 10th, 1st year, and 2nd year classes to ensure they shared similar academic challenges and study burdens.

Inclusion Criteria

- Participants aged 14 to 18 years were included in the study.
- Data was collected from students enrolled in the 9th and 10th grades, as well as those in the 1st and 2nd years of college.
- Only mainstream students were selected for participation.

Exclusion Criteria

- Participants with disabilities or disorders were excluded from the study.
- Participants enrolled in university and middle school were excluded.

Measures

Perceived Parental Styles Scale (PPSS)

To assess perceived parental styles, the Indigenous Scale of Perceived Parental Styles, developed by Saleem and Mahmood in 2017, was utilized. This 24-item scale follows a 4-point Likert format, ranging from 1 (never) to 4 (always). It measures two key dimensions: warmth and control. Warmth reflects parental love, care, and affection toward children. Control reflects the strictness, boundaries, and restrictions of parents on their children. The scale demonstrates strong reliability, with an internal consistency of 0.89.

Sedentary Behavior Scale (SBS)

To assess sedentary behaviors in adolescents, an indigenous scale of sedentary behavior was employed in this study. This two-factor scale evaluates both a lack of physical activity and screen time. Developed by Munir and Jabeen in 2023 for Pakistani adolescents, it consists of 13 items. Items 1 to 4 assess the absence of physical activity, while items 5 to 13 measure screen usage. The scale follows a four-point Likert format, ranging from 1 (never) to 4 (too much).

Wong and Law Emotional Intelligence Scale (WLEIS)

The Wong and Law Emotional Intelligence Scale (WLEIS) was used to assess emotional intelligence. Originally developed by Wong and Law in 2002 in Columbia, its validity and reliability were later tested on Pakistani adolescents by Masood and Akhtar in 2023. This 16-item scale follows a 7-point Likert format, ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 7 (strongly agree). With an internal consistency of 0.88, the scale demonstrates high reliability.

School Children Problem Scale (SCPS-PA)

To assess academic problems, the Indigenous Scale of School Children's Problems was utilized. This self-report measure was developed by Mahmood and Saleem in 2011 and comprises six factors: anxiousness, academic problems, aggression, social withdrawal, feelings of rejection, and psychosomatic issues. However, for this study, only the academic problems domain, consisting of 8 items, was used. The scale follows a four-point Likert format, ranging from 1 (never) to 4 (often). With an internal consistency of 0.79, it is considered a reliable measure.

Procedure

This study aimed to explore the relationship between perceived parental styles, sedentary behavior, emotional intelligence, and academic problems in adolescents. Furthermore, the relationship between warmth and control parenting styles with study variables was also explored. Ethical approval to conduct the study was taken from the University of Management and Technology (UMT). Data was collected from government and private schools and colleges of Lahore from May 2024 to August 2024. After getting permission from the institutes the study was conducted. A purposive sampling technique was used to conduct the study. Participants ranging between the age range of 14 to 18 years were included. Participants from mainstream education were included. Participants with any disabilities and disorders were excluded from the study. Data was not collected from university students. The participants were given informed consent, and their voluntary participation was ensured. The participants were allowed to withdraw from the study whenever they wanted. Initially, a pilot study was conducted on 25 students to ensure any underlying ambiguities and difficulties. After that, it was explored that questionnaire readability was good, participants understood it and no difficulties were found. Then the main study was conducted on 300 participants including an equal number of boys and girls. The data was analyzed using SPSS_21. Frequencies, percentage, mean, and standard deviation were used on demographics while correlation was used to find out the relationship between study variables.

Results

Descriptive Analysis

Table 1

Socio-demographic Characteristics of the Participants (N=300)

Variable	<i>F</i>	%
Gender		
Males	154	51.3%
Females	146	48.7%
Age of participant		
14-15 years	86	28.7%
16-17 years	132	44%
18-19 years	82	27.3%

Education of participant		
9 th	100	33.3%
10 th	50	16.7%
1 st year	62	20.7%
2 nd year	88	29.3%
Mother education		
Illiterate	25	8.3%
Matric	68	22.7%
Intermediate	85	28.3%
Bachelors	69	23%
Masters and above	53	17.7%
Father education		
Illiterate	13	4.3%
Matric	68	22.7%
Intermediate	62	20.7%
Bachelors	92	30.7%
Masters and above	65	21.7%
Father occupation		
Businessman	93	31.0%
Government job	70	23.3%
Private job	85	28.3%
Other	52	17.3%
Mother Occupation		
Housewife	237	79%
Working woman	57	19%
Family system		
Nuclear	193	64.3%
Joint	106	35.3%
Birth order		
Firstborn	98	32.7%
Middle child	135	45.0%
Last born	53	17.7%
Only child	14	4.7%

The table illustrates that males (51%) were reported slightly more than females (48%). Additionally, the majority of participants fell within the 16-17 age range (44%), followed by 14-15 years (28.7%) and 18-19 years (27.3%). A greater number of participants belonged to nuclear families (64%) compared to joint families (35%). Regarding education, most participants were in the 9th grade (33%), while 16.7% were in the 10th grade, 20.7% in the 1st year, and 29.3% in the 2nd year. Mothers' education was most commonly at the intermediate level (28%), while 8.3% were illiterate, 22.7% had completed matric, 23% held a bachelor's degree, and 17.7% had a master's degree or higher. Fathers'

education was highest at the bachelor's level (30%), while 4.3% were illiterate, 22.7% had completed matric, 20.7% had an intermediate education, and 21.7% held a master's degree or higher. In terms of occupation, most fathers were businessmen (30%), followed by those in government jobs (23.3%), private jobs (28.3%), and other professions (17.3%). The majority of mothers were housewives (79%), while 19% were employed. Finally, birth order distribution showed that most participants were middle children (45%), while 32.7% were firstborns, 17.7% were lastborns, and 4.7% were only children.

Table 2

Mean and Standard Deviation of No. of Siblings, Father's and Mother's Age(N=300)

Variables	M	SD
Father age	46.51	7.01
Mother age	41.89	6.01

Note. M= mean, SD= standard deviation
 The above table indicates that no.of siblings has M=3.57 and SD= 1.37 while the father's age has

M=26.51 and SD=7.01. Moreover, the mother's age is M=41.89 and SD=6.01.

Normality of the Data

Table 3

Mean, 5% Trimmed Mean, Skewness and Kurtosis of Perceived Parenting Styles, Sedentary Behavior, Emotional Intelligence, And Academic Problems (N=300)

Variables	M	Median	5% trimmed mean	Skewness	Kurtosis	<i>a</i>
PPSS	75.39	77.00	75.76	-0.7	0.96	0.78
WPS-1	41.68	42.00	41.98	-0.85	1.03	
CPS-2	33.70	35.00	33.95	-0.69	0.47	
SBS	35.53	36.00	35.54	-0.04	0.06	0.78
SU -1	24.46	25.00	24.47	-0.02	-0.27	
LPA-2	11.07	11.00	11.09	-0.21	-0.23	
WLEIS	69.94	71.15	70.48	-0.39	1.14	0.81
SCPS-AP	20.03	20.00	20.04	0.39	2.32	0.70

Note. PPSS= perceived parenting styles, PPSS-1 = warmth Parenting, PPSS-2= control parenting, SBS = Sedentary Behavior Scale, SBS-1= screen usage, SBS-2= lack of physical activity, WLEIS = Wong and Law Emotional Intelligence Scale, SCPS-AP= School Children Problem Scale Academic Problems
 The findings suggest that the mean and 5% trimmed mean values for PPSS, SBS, WLEIS,

and SCPS are nearly identical. Additionally, the mean and median values are closely aligned across all variables. Furthermore, the skewness and kurtosis values fall within the range of +3 to -3, indicating that the dataset follows a normal distribution. Moreover, the above table shows that PPSS has 0.78, SBS has 0.78, WLEIS has 0.81, and SCPS-AP has 0.70 Cronbach alpha value, which shows that all scales have good internal consistency

Table 4: Inter-factor Correlation Among Perceived Parenting Styles, Sedentary Behavior, Emotional Intelligence, And Academic Problems (N= 300)

Scale	M	SD	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1 Warmth parenting style	41.68	5.74	---	---	---	---	---	---	---
2 Control parenting style	33.70	5.52	.41***	---	---	---	---	---	---
3 Sedentary behavior scale	35.53	6.89	-.19	.00	---	---	---	---	---
4 Screen usage	24.46	5.49	-.05	-.58	.94***	---	---	---	---
5 Lack of physical activity	11.07	2.48	.63	.13*	.68***	.41***	---	---	---
6 Emotional intelligence scale	69.94	14.98	.25***	.25***	.03	-.02	-.12*	---	---
7 Academic problems	20.03	5.21	-.11*	.00	.25***	.25***	.15**	-.23***	---

Note. WPS-1 = warmth parenting, CPS-2= control parenting, SBS = Sedentary Behavior Scale, SU-1= screen usage, LPA-2= lack of physical activity, WLEIS = Wong and Law Emotional Intelligence Scale, SCPS-AP= School Children Problem Scale Academic Problems

* $p \leq 0.05$, ** $p \leq 0.01$, *** $p \leq .001$

Table 4 shows that warmth parenting has a significant negative correlation with academic problems ($r = -0.11$, $p < 0.05$). Moreover, warmth parenting had a positive and significant relationship with emotional intelligence ($r = 0.25$, $p < 0.001$) while it has a significant negative relationship with academic problems ($r = 0.11$, $p < 0.05$). Control parenting was negatively correlated with screen usage and positively correlated with lack of physical activity. SBS had a significant positive relationship with academic problems ($r = 0.25$, $p < 0.001$). However, screen usage was significantly positively correlated with academic problems ($r = 0.25$, $p < 0.001$). Lack of physical activity had a significant negative relationship with emotional intelligence ($r = 0.12$, $p < 0.01$) and a significant positive relationship with academic problems ($r = 0.15$, $p < 0.001$). Furthermore, emotional intelligence and academic problems had a significant negative relationship with each other ($r = -0.23$, $p < 0.001$).

Discussion

Life is always considered dynamic with its own ups and downs. Every transition of life comes up with its challenges and difficulties. Similarly transition from adolescence stage from childhood has its own challenges and different individuals react differently towards it. So, this study aimed to explore the bio, psycho, and social model of adolescents' lives by exploring the relationship between perceived parenting styles, sedentary behavior, emotional intelligence, and academic problems.

The results revealed that warmth parenting was significantly negatively correlated with academic problems. Garcia et al., 2020 revealed that warmth parents show love and affection towards their children and are actively involved in their child's activities. Thus, they are also actively involved in their child's academic matters thus helping them in their academic progress. In this way, warmth parenting can reduce academic problems in children. It was also explored that

control parenting, sedentary behavior, and academic problems had a significant positive relation with each other (Teuber et al., 2022). The study revealed that due to high demands and strict boundaries, controlled parenting restricts their children's ability to explore the world thus they have high levels of screen time. So, children are more involved in sedentary behaviors. Furthermore, due to the lack of involvement, children feel helpless in their academic struggles which increases their academic problems (Saleem et al., 2015). Furthermore, the study also revealed that sedentary behavior had a positive relationship with emotional intelligence. The literature revealed that students using screens for study purposes and spending time on YouTube lectures have high levels of emotional intelligence because it increases their thinking abilities and helps them develop a better understanding of academic topics (Martinez et al., 2020). Whereas emotional intelligence had a significant negative relationship with academic problems. The literature also supported that emotional intelligence affects the cognitive abilities of students including critical and abstract thinking. Moreover, it also improves the individual's ability to reason and evaluate things. Thus, emotional intelligence helps improve students' academic performance. So emotional intelligence plays a crucial role in lowering the levels of academic problems (Supervía et al., 2022).

Limitations and recommendations

The data was collected from one city of Pakistan which can affect the generalizability of results. A qualitative approach should be used to explore the subjective opinions of students on screen time and parenting styles. Longitudinal study should be used to explore the changing biological, emotional, and social dynamics of individuals.

Implications

This study will contribute to understanding the underlying factors influencing academic performance and challenges during adolescence. It will raise awareness among psychologists and other mental health professionals about the significance of parental involvement in a child's life and how children perceive their parents' responses.

Conclusion

Vygotsky's social-cultural theory explains the importance of social and cultural aspects in shaping one's identity and thought processes. Similarly in today's world screen usage and electronic devices are playing crucial roles in defining the social interaction of individuals thus helping them learn new things by broadening their environmental opportunities. Similarly, the results of the current study revealed the importance of parent-child interaction and social interaction in helping individuals in their academic matters. So the results of the current study will help future researchers in exploring the positive aspects of screen usage while it will also help the policy makers of academic institutions to incorporate new learning styles in the curriculum to enhance the learning of students.

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